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Adaptation and Resistance of Female Congregations towards the Communist Authorities in Poland between 1945 – 1989

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Introduction

From 1944 when Poland was under communist rule, two kinds of attitude existed in Polish society: adaptation and resistance. Adaptation is understood to be a social attitude that aims for relative peace and fulfils the desires of both individuals and whole groups, whereas resistance is a spontaneous, unordered and unmanaged protest against an existing political and ideological order, often connected with the defence of traditional values.¹ These attitudes – adaptation and resistance – spread in the People's Republic of Poland because of the stability of power of the Polish United Workers' Party, as well as common beliefs about the lack of alternatives to the existing order of Europe's division.² Krystyna Kersten, while analysing these social attitudes, noted that they were present in almost every aspect of life, including political decisions, election of intellectuals and the actions of millions of ordinary people. *Adaptation and resistance grew from the same stem: they were driven by the imperative of the nation's existence in biological and cultural aspects and the role of the Polish state in protecting the material and cultural lives of Poles.*

The coincidence of adaptation and resistance being together in different aspects – intellectual, emotional, moral – resulted in deep consequences.

1 FRISZKE, A.: *Opozycja polityczna w PRL 1945 – 1980*. Londyn 1994, p. 5.

2 FRISZKE, A.: *Przystosowanie i opór. Studia z dziejów PRL*. Warszawa 2007, p. 124.

*It guaranteed survival but for many it happened to be destructive and caused spiritual devastation, as well as deprivation as a result of unlimited compromise.*³

1. The Catholic Church's situation in the People's Republic of Poland

Until 1948 (until the political opposition was crushed) the attitudes of communist authorities towards the Catholic Church and convents in Poland were pragmatic, whereas the Church had a very realistic approach towards the authorities. It tried to avoid direct involvement in existing political battles and concentrate on building organisational structures. From 1948 there was a fundamental change in attitude towards the Catholic Church. The authorities aimed to defiantly weaken the Church and keep it under control. They also undertook action that aimed to separate the Church from the State. This meant that faith became a private matter (especially after removing religion from schools). In the meantime, atheistic propaganda was proclaimed, especially among young people. Indescribable but constant war was taking place between the State and the Church. It had very different stages but only one goal: to isolate the Church and prevent it from having an impact on Polish opinion.⁴ In August 1949, a 'Decree of protection of freedom of conscience and denomination' was issued. Technically this document, just like its title shows, was meant to create a lawful guarantee of freedom of denominations in Poland. In reality the different authorities used some of the regulations both to make the Church's life more difficult and to repress the clergy and secular people.⁵

The right person for the Church happened to be Cardinal Stefan Wyszyński, the Primate of Poland. From the beginning of his service in Warsaw, he proved to have an excellent skill and ability to put out conflicts. Wanting to *gain time in order to increase the power to protect the Divine position*⁶, on 14 April 1950, Wyszyński and the Episcopate signed an

3 KERSTEN, K.: *Między wyzwoleniem a zniewoleniem. Polska 1944 – 1956*. Londyn 1993, p. 14.

4 KISIELEWSKI, S.: *Na czym polega socjalizm? Stosunki Kościół-państwo w PRL*. Poznań 1990, p. 86.

5 DUDEK, A. – GRYZ, R.: *Komuniści i Kościół w Polsce (1945-1989)*. Kraków 2003, p. 43.

6 WYSZYŃSKI, S.: *Zapiski więzienne*. Bydgoszcz 1990, p. 15.

agreement. For the authorities this act had a propaganda value and enabled them to engage in controversy with international public opinion about the persecution of the Church in Poland. The authorities were hoping to break psychological barriers (signing a document) with the Episcopate, which didn't have anything in common with reality. They were hoping that this would create more possibilities for the Church's hierarchy to take part in a propaganda campaign⁷. Thanks to the inflexible attitudes of Cardinal Wyszyński and his *non possumus*⁸, the authorities were unable to fulfil the programme of 'loyalty' in the Catholic Church in Poland. The first years of coexistence of the Catholic Church and communist authorities in Poland had a big impact on the situation and future relations between State and Church. For all post-Stalinist leaders of the Polish United Workers' Party this time was proof of the failure and political harmfulness of an extremely repressive model of politics towards different denominations. On the other hand, events from 1945 until 1955 made bishops and clergy realise that they had to prepare themselves for the permanent politics that, using different methods, aimed for secularisation and atheisation of society and breach of the Church's autonomy.⁹

2. Religious convents in the People's Republic of Poland

World War II had a big impact on religious orders and congregations in Poland; it thinned out the number of nuns. Due to the war devastation and arrangements made by the Big Three, convents lost their houses and possessions, especially on Kresy, but they gained the respect and trust of society instead. This was a result of their clear and uncompromising attitudes of coming to the aid of those who needed help in occupied country. When freedom was announced (May 1945), nuns struggling with difficult material situations started to live a normal life and reactivated different kinds of institution – charitable, educational, childcare and academic – depending on the congregation's character and local situation. They started to create day care centres, nurseries, orphanages (especially for post-war orphans), primary schools, high schools, dormitories and canteens, not

7 DUDEK, A. – GRYZ, R.: *Komuniści i Kościół w Polsce*, p. 57.

8 An Episcopal Memorial to Bolesław Bierut form 8th May 1953. In: RAINA, P.: *Kościół w PRL, Kościół katolicki a państwo w świetle dokumentów 1945 – 1989*. Poznań 1994, p. 426.

9 DUDEK, A. – GRYZ, R.: *Komuniści i Kościół w Polsce*, pp. 98 – 99.

to mention helping at hospitals, health centres, parishes and among the poor or those who were under moral threat. In the first period, authorities supported convents, however this was only a temporary kindness. Subsequently the communist government didn't plan for congregations to carry out free social activities but planned to gradually limit their work, create closed enclaves and completely liquidate nuns' work.¹⁰

The Primate of Poland, Cardinal Stefan Wyszyński, who had a great sense of the situation in which the Church of Poland found itself, was also aware that religious orders and congregations would have to play an important role in this battle "for God, Truth and Freedom". He was aware that this role could be significant, creative and effective as long as it was carried out by everyone. That is why he wanted to create in Poland, as he said, "*a uniform army of souls devoted to God, sacrificial souls living according to the evangelic spirit, spirit of their founders ready to face the atheism in order to save a faith among the nation especially among the young generation.*"¹¹ The Primate was looking at not only how to defend a congregation's assets and common attitudes towards the politics of the state authorities but also how to develop a spiritual and intellectual level. Moreover the role that convents played in Polish society in this extraordinary situation always changing and threatened both the nation's faith and education of the younger generation.

The Catholics in Poland were treated as second-rate citizens (limited in their ability to get promotion, even if they kept a loyal attitude). However nuns were treated even worse as third-rate citizens, being continuously pushed into the dregs of social life, not only without any chance of promotion but also without the fundamental rights and freedom guaranteed to every Pole by the Constitution.¹² "*A special politics of discrimination is used towards religious orders and congregations*" – Wyszyński pointed out to the authorities – "*to which our Nation in its history and society owe*

10 A protocol from a session of the Commission KC on Clergy Affairs in 26th of July 1961. In: *Tajne dokumenty Państwo-Kościół 1960 – 1980*. London 1996, pp. 17 – 28.

11 ŁACZKA, A. (ed.): *Wspomnienia o współpracy między zakonnej Zgromadzeń Zakonnych Żeńskich w Polsce po II wojnie światowej do 1960 r.*, Cz. II. Warszawa 1986, p. 5.

12 "*A situation of the monastic clergy is very uncertain and dangerous. Religious orders are limited in their activities. Moreover they are prevent from doing all kind of work that they used to do everywhere and according to their vocation. By using unpleasant political methods of pressure the authorities are aiming to expropriate religious orders from existence funds and apostolic work*". In: An Episcopal Memorial to the government of People's Republic of Poland 15th of April 1959. In: RAINA, P.: *Kościół w PRL*, t. 1, p. 37.

a lot".¹³ Nuns were systematically deprived of carrying out apostolic work as well as taking on any other work.¹⁴ They were refused the opportunity to get qualifications¹⁵, use social welfare benefits such as health care, social insurance or a retirement pension¹⁶, and tax regulations were also used very instrumentally.¹⁷ This planned atheisation affected all of the congregations' activities.¹⁸ The process was institutional and lawful. Moreover this battle with the religious orders' work was happening in the face of the law.¹⁹

"The most painful and irritable, because it discriminates against clergies" – wrote the Primate, Stefan Wyszyński, in his letter to Prime Minister Boleslaw Bierut about disobeying the rights by civil servants – *"is the politics of finished facts with methods insulting the democratic state power.*

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- 13 An Episcopal Memorial to the government of People's Republic of Poland 15th of April 1959. In: RAINA, P.: *Kościół w PRL*, t. 1, p. 700.
- 14 *"Nuns from female congregations are removed from hospitals and charitable institutions, in which they worked for a long time with a big dedication and heroic time for the sick, orphans and lonely. With no regardless of their present and future situation they are deprived of their property support."* In: An Episcopal Memorial, p. 34.
- 15 *"There wasn't any place for nuns at schools. They were deprived of teaching secular subjects so there no need to educate nuns to became teachers. The only university that allowed religious people to study in socialism was The Catholic University of Lublin."* KACZMAREK, E.: *Dlaczego przeszkadzały?* Warszawa 2007, p. 148.
- 16 Those solutions having a discrimination character are seen in regulations telling about the lack of ability to insure due to the fact of being a religious person and carrying out an apostolic work. STANISZ, P.: Rola przepisów regulujących ubezpieczenie społeczne duchownych w realizacji polityki wyznaniowej państwa w latach 1945-1989. In: MEZGLEWSKI, A. – STANISZ, P. – ORDON, M. (eds.): *Prawo i polityka wyznaniowa w Polsce Ludowej*. Lublin 2005, pp. 272 – 273; see BACH, T.: Ubezpieczenie społeczne osób duchownych i zakonnych w PRL (1945 – 1989). In: *Kościół i prawo*, t. 13, Lublin 1998.
- 17 A legal person of the Catholic Church including convents weren't treated by the authorities of the People's Republic of Poland as social organizations within the meaning of tax law, they were treated as institutions focusing on profit only. STANISŁAWSKI, T.: Wykorzystanie opodatkowania Kościoła w polityce wyznaniowej PRL. In: *Prawo i polityka wyznaniowa w Polsce Ludowej*. In: MEZGLEWSKI, A. – STANISZ, P. – ORDON, M. (eds.): *Prawo i polityka wyznaniowa w Polsce Ludowej*, p. 265.
- 18 It is worth to show some figures to illustrate this process. Between 1949 – 1967 80 monastic schools, 263 orphanages, 680 nurseries, 73 community centres and 46 day-care centres were liquidated. Out of 276 hospitals, only 93 remained. Monastic hospitals were nationalized. DĘBOWSKA, K.: Kardynał Stefan Wyszyński a zakony żeńskie. Co zgromadzenia żeńskie zawdzięczają Prymasowi Tysiąclecia? In: *Institute życia konsekrowanego i stowarzyszeń życia apostołskiego w hołdzie Prymasowi Tysiąclecia*. Warszawa 2001.
- 19 ZUBER, B. W. – BACH, T. M.: Ograniczenia w realizacji własnego charyzmatu przez instytuty zakonne w okresie rządów totalitarnych w Polsce. In: *Roczniki Nauk Prawnych*, 1994, t. 4, p. 87.

*Those methods, based on some civil servants' ruthlessness and zeal, aimed straight to a law and order because they determined and ruined the chance to defend and recall. They were the reason why the State Council and Ministry Council Resolution from 14th of December 1950, in a case of considering and arranging recall and grievance, is becoming a dead letter for those categories of wronged [...] Clergies are not considered to be citizens with full rights".*²⁰ The Episcopate was protecting monastic life. It was aware that a battle with religious orders was part of the main repertoire among most of the regime, which could undertake a battle with the Church at any time.²¹ *"Monasteries' situation" – wrote bishops in a memorial to Boleslaw Bierut – "is one of the most alarming matters in the current Church's situation. Without any rights to do charity work, without any of their own properties, suffering from persecution, custody and numerous commissions, monasteries in Poland are in an extremely difficult situation".*²²

The authorities, free from the uncomfortable bonds of the Concordat, which was terminated in September 1945, gradually introduced legal provisions that aimed to eliminate all kinds of religious order activities. The People's Republic of Poland Constitution enacted in 1952 guaranteed freedom of conscience and denomination in article 82. However atheisation devepoled because constitutional rules about religious law being under the influence of atheism were interpreted very freely. As a result, the regulations of the religious legislation in relation to the religious orders were broken instead of guaranteeing rights and freedom based on the Constitution.²³

One can ask: Where does the kind of law exist that gives the main factors (the authorities) the right to make an instant accusation against the religious hierarchy, clergy and peaceful people? Why is a person who works peacefully considered to be a worse citizen and punished with impunity and publicly admonished only because he believes in God, trusts Him and wants to remain under the religion and moral guidance of the Catholic Church?²⁴

20 The Primate S. Wyszyński's letter from 22nd of May 1953 to the Prime Minister B. Bierut about disobeying the law by the civil servants. In: RAINA, P.: *Kościół w PRL*, p. 429.

21 *A memory about an inter-religious orders cooperation*, p. 31.

22 A letter from 12th of September 1950 referred to B. Bierut about the harm caused to the Church. In: RAINA, P.: *Kościół w PRL*, t. 1, p. 253.

23 PIETRZAK, M.: *Prawo wyznaniowe*. Warszawa 1993, p. 157.

24 *An Episcopal Memorial to the government of People's Republic of Poland*, p. 692.

3. Inter-religious orders' cooperation as an example of effective resistance

In November 1945 representatives of monastic communities turned to the Polish Primate, Cardinal August Hlond and showed him the importance of making an agreement between religious orders in order to create uniform attitudes toward the communist state authorities. The Primate called a congress in Cracow (24-25 January 1946) for all superior and provincial generals. This congress took place at Ursulines of the Roman Union, where 124 nuns from 53 convents gathered together. It became very significant because it started, according to the Primate's recommendation, a united front and uniform attitudes towards the state authorities. As a result, a special commission (Committee on Inter-religious Orders Agreement) was created which was based in Warsaw.²⁵ Between 1946 and 1949 informal groups of inter-religious orders cooperation, which didn't have any organisational form, were created in individual dioceses. The most active were religious orders in the Diocese of Cracow under Cardinal Adamo Stefano Sapięha's supervision. At the beginning, meetings took place at Ursulines Sisters but due to increasing danger from the state authorities, the location was changed every three months.²⁶ The existence and future of congregations were more and more uncertain every year.

After 1948 when authority regulations started to threaten the existence of congregations, it was clear that convents would have to resist the attack coming from 'ours'. At that time there was a need for joint action and common agreement. It was believed that being under one church's leadership in close connection with the Church's hierarchy is the only way to face up to enemies fighting with God, Church and religion in their own country. Trusting the Church's hierarchy absolutely guaranteed, without any doubts, survival and victory. There was a need for unity and a big effort was made by the inter-religious orders cooperation to achieve this unity.²⁷ On 9 March 1950, in the church of the Visitation Order in

25 The congress was very significant. It started, according to the Primate's recommendation a joint front and made an action towards the state authorities uniform. The congress made clear where the authorities are aiming, what type of methods they use to achieve this goal and how to prevent this. In: *Wspomnienia o współpracy między zakonnej Zgromadzeń Zakonnych Żeńskich w Polsce po II wojnie światowej do 1960 r.*

26 KACZMAREK, E.: *Dlaczego przeszkadzały?*, p. 132.

27 *Wspomnienia o współpracy między zakonnej Zgromadzeń Zakonnych Żeńskich w Polsce po II wojnie światowej do 1960 r.*

Warsaw near Krakowskie Przedmieście, behind the a closed and guarded door, superior generals met with the secretary of the Episcopate, Bishop Zygmunt Choromański, who pointed out the dangers to monastic life (as a consequence of the politics of the state authorities) and gave some useful instructions. The next nationwide meeting with superior generals present took place in Warsaw in August 1950. Then the idea of an inter-religious orders agreement was specified and became the Department of Monastic Affairs at the Secretariat of the Polish Primate, which was directed by priest Bronisław Dąbrowski, later archbishop and long-term general secretary of the Polish Episcopate, followed by Alojzy Żuchowski (the Pallottines). In order to make all religious classes in Poland more dynamic, Cardinal Wyszyński, established an unknown institution: dioceses referents²⁸ which firstly appointed himself. Due to the diocese referents' work, all the inspiration and indications of Cardinal Wyszyński reached every convent in Poland. Commissions were the bodies which supported the Department of Monastic Affairs were. At first they were called departments and were founded by the Superior Generals Consul of Higher Female Religious Orders.²⁹ These commissions³⁰ were: educational³⁰, parish³¹, Marian³², nurs-

28 A Department of Monastic Affairs realized that it wasn't able to support all of the congregations spread all over different dioceses as well as it wasn't able to communicate them quickly about important matters. In order to coordinate a work and give a better course in dealing with different matters The Primate established dioceses referents which had a varied work. They had to pass all the official instructions made by the Department of Monastic Affairs and made sure they were fulfilled. They also had to carry out both educational action for nuns and concentration in order to deepen a spiritual and monastic life. The first meeting for dioceses referents took place in 11th of March 1953. *Wspomnienia o współpracy między zakonnej Zgromadzeń Zakonnych Żeńskich w Polsce po II wojnie światowej do 1960 r.*, p. 22.

29 BAR, J.: Konferencje Wyższych Przełożonych zakonów w Polsce. In: *Prawo Kanoniczne*, Vol. 23, 1980, No. 3-4, p. 145.

30 An educational commission was founded in 1950, a few headteachers of monastic schools were members of this commission. The main goal was to communicate in order to create uniform attitudes towards a state authorities' order as well as share experiences, discuss problems connecting with work at school, work on programs and organize a day of concentration for headteachers, teachers and children.

31 A parish commission was founded in 1951 as an answers to different problems happening among nuns who worked in parishes. The main goal was to organize trainings as well as helping nuns who started their work at parishes.

32 A Marian commission was established by the Polish Primate in 10 February 1959. The main goal was to coordinate all of the activities, spiritual and apostolic connecting with spreading a Marian cult. *Wspomnienia o współpracy między zakonnej Zgromadzeń Zakonnych Żeńskich w Polsce po II wojnie światowej do 1960 r.*, p. 222 – 232.

ing³³ and a separate commission of congregations with no religious habits (clothing).³⁴

Due to the huge commitment of its director, priest Bronisław Dąbrowski, and the competent and devoted work of nuns (directed to this work by Cardinal Wyszyński), the Department of Monastic Affairs soon became an information point³⁵, a centre for discussion and sharing experiences and what's more an important organ representing convents to the secular authorities.³⁶ It is worth mentioning that accustoming congregations to inter-religious orders cooperation wasn't easy. Some people thought that this cooperation, recommended by Cardinal Wyszyński, was an attack on the internal autonomy of convents. The more the state authorities threatened convents, the more they realised the importance of joint action which enabled convents to exchange experiences and support each other in different situations. "*We all work*" – said the Primate – "*in order to unite our monastic attitudes so we can fulfil a task appropriate to every monastic family and so we can protect the right of monastic life in Poland always threatened, always uncertain*".³⁷

An initiative of inter-religious orders cooperation happened to be very useful for the whole of monastic life in Poland under communism. Due to the considerable help and recommendation of the Department of Monastic

33 A nursing commission started its work in February 1960.

34 A commission of congregations with no religious habit was founded by the Polish Primate to replace a current Consul of congregations with no religious habit founded by Honorat. The main reason for this reorganization was to make a closer connection between congregations with no religious habit and Superiors Generals Conferees of Female Religious Orders in Poland. The legal character of section is based on principles regulating inter-religious orders work of Female State of Perfection in Poland approved by the Polish Primate in 12th of May 1960. Members of this section were appointed by the Polish Primate with a decree of 10th of September 1965 among candidates chosen by the Higher Superior Generals of Female Congregations with no religious habit founded by Honorat in 12th of May 1965. In: Archive of Congregation of Daughters of Mary Immaculate (further only ACDMI), Commission of Congregations with no religious habit, signature (further only sign.) B. XVIII, I. 2, documents about appointing the commission of nuns from congregations with no religious habit by the Council of Higher Superior Generals of Female Monastic Congregations in Poland.

35 ACDMI, f. the State Authorities, sign. B. XV, I. 1-3, A legal instruction based on regulations as at the date of 10th of November 1952.

36 *Wspomnienia o współpracy między zakonnej Zgromadzeń Zakonnych Żeńskich w Polsce po II wojnie światowej do 1960 r.*, p. 22.

37 The Primate speech in 2 August 1958 during the meeting with higher superior generals and a protonotary apostolic B. Filipiakiem, the auditor of the Secret Roman Rota.

Affairs, which was obeyed by Polish nuns, they were able to resist the destructive activities of the authorities. Instructions about how to complete a statistical questionnaire³⁸, run a housing register³⁹, carry on a conversation with administrative authorities in offices⁴⁰ or welcome an officer of the Security Service of the Ministry of Internal Affairs into monastic houses were sent by diocese referents to every convent in Poland. These instructions were very successful in forming resistance attitudes. A different kind of resistance towards an order of communist authorities was to refuse to keep the accounting and inventory records of religious orders.

During an Episcopal meeting on 7 May 1951, bishops raised an issue about danger for convents from state authorities. Firm resistance was recommended, such as an energetic protest or a written appeal to a higher institution demanding an answer based on the law guaranteed by the Constitution. Wyszyński was convinced that convents shouldn't give any pretexts for the authorities to think that they were afraid because this may lead to more attacks.⁴¹

In this situation, the Primate was forced to make a new action plan due to the intensive attack on monastic life in Poland. General principles about monastic houses were included in three points. First, they should resist as long as possible. Second, they should leave the state institutions but defend their own. Finally, every congregation should decide which house they could give up first and which they could lease in whole or in part. It was recommended that nuns who were removed from state institutions should be given a chance to work in different monastic families. Congregations with small communities were encouraged not to give up their institutions but to undertake work instead. A second part of the analysis was related to methods and conditions while undertaking a job. The general rule in this case was to resist a common monastic life. In cases where state factors forced nuns to work, they suggested undertaking work at home and signing an agreement explaining all the norms which enable nuns to carry on

38 ACDMI, the State Authorities, sign. B. XV, I. 1-3,

39 Ibid.

40 Ibid., How nuns should behave in case of a personally summon to appear before the office.

41 Archive of Institute of National Remembrance (further only A IPN) BU, signature (further only sign.) 01283/902, An information number 1/119 from the provincial conference from 31 July 1952.

their monastic exercises⁴². The last problem under discussion was religious habits (clothing). It was said that complete renouncement of religious habits was unacceptable. One shouldn't change the habit itself but only minimise the material.⁴³

4. In defence of religious orders' possessions

In January 1950, the authorities decided to nationalise the diocese institutions 'Caritas' and take over all of their possessions. The act about filling ecclesiastical positions was substituted with different options, prepared and accepted during a meeting on 23 February 1950: as we can read in the protocol it should be taking over church possessions by the state and creating a Church Fund.⁴⁴ Lack of any notice of competence and a way of appointing the Church Fund become the next instrument of pressure when dealing with the Church⁴⁵. An act about 'goods of death hand' introduced legal status and congregations were loosing their own properties and households which maintained a lot of religious orders; especially novitiates and formation houses. Monastic houses were allowed to have only five hectares of land. The nuns fought back – they demanded respect for their right to keep possessions. By using economical instruments the authorities wanted to penetrate the Church's internal structures, especially religious orders, and become their legislator.

When the act was issued it began to be enforced. Small commissions started to appear in convents in order to sign a protocol about taking over properties.⁴⁶ Civil servants had the text of a protocol about taking over

42 KACZMAREK, E.: *Dlaczego przeszkadzały?*, p. 135.

43 An Archive of Polish Episcopal Secretary, sign. 23/I, Issues about monastic houses, pp. 5 – 6.

44 An Archive of New Act (further only AAN) Warszaw, f. KC PZPR (Central Committee of the Polish United Workers' Party), sign. 1639, A Protocol from the meeting of KC PZPR 23. 2. 1950.

45 WINIARCZYK-KOSSAKOWSKA, M.: *Przejęcie przez państwo „dóbr martwej ręki”*, p. 58.

46 In a general house of Congregation of Daughters of Mary Immaculate a commission in the presence of sister L. Kamińską tried to take possessions to the benefit of the state in Nowym Mieście n. Pilicą by Rawskiej and Rawskiej 22 street. (...) at the end of a protocol an officer wrote: "Possessions belong to the Congregation of Daughters of Mary Immaculate "Caritas" in Nowe Miasto n. Pilica, according to the situation mentioned above, are being transferred to the management board of state. A member of the congregation who was present during the protocol was signing refused to sign it." In: AAN, f. UdSW, sign.

properties written on a typewriter and they had to fill it with specific data. They made a list of houses, living and dead goods, supplies of root crops and fodder. There were a lot of irregularities and misuse in the action of taking over monastic properties. Commissions that visited convents very often took over everything that belonged to them, interpreting the act as they pleased.⁴⁷

The Episcopate undertook action in order to protect possessions belonging to congregations. As a result, monastic houses were able to keep land of five hectares. However, the realisation of a promise was based on a political assessment of particular houses, superior generals or the whole congregation. All the decisions that were made by the authorities showed a negative attitude towards convents. According to the list of appeals directed to state offices by congregations, fulfilling a decree on taking over a church's possessions became an instrument of state politics conducted towards congregations. The main goal was to set a limit on the financial base of religious orders and its enforcement was supposed to persuade nuns to have a positive attitude towards all the changes happening in Poland.⁴⁸

Cardinal Wyszyński encouraged nuns to be brave and assume a firm attitude to defending their possessions. He said calmly to them: *bear suffering and harm with peace, ready to forgive, but remember do not eat Polish bread for free because it is properly earned by You. You have the right to keep your houses and to protect within members of your congregation devastated by social work.*⁴⁹

5. "There is no place for nuns in schools"

According to the authorities, allowing nuns to work in schools was dangerous for education. There was the burden of the liability not only for spreading a convent's atmosphere in schools but also for bringing up children in the clerical spirit. They were accused of a lack of ideological attitudes and a hostile attitude towards political changes happening in Poland.

5c/3, A protocol of taking over possessions belong to the Congregation of Daughters of Mary Immaculate in Nowe Miasto n. Pilica to the benefit of the state.

47 KACZMAREK, E.: *Dlaczego przeszkadzały?*, p. 99.

48 *Ibid.*, p. 102.

49 *Memories about an inter-religious orders cooperation of Female Congregations in Poland after World War II till 1960*, p. 31.

One of the ways to restore schools in Poland was to take away from the Church and its institutions (including religious orders) the right to teach. This action against monastic schools was planned during a meeting of the Politburo of the Polish United Workers' Party and carried out by the Ministry of Education. In the first stage of an action against monastic schools the Ministry of Education dealt with primary schools. Based on the information gathered, the Political Office made a concrete decision. It was decided that until 1 September 1949, all nuns teaching secular subjects and performing an educational function should be removed. Even if the negative attitude of nuns towards the People's Republic of Poland was never found, they were suspected of having one.⁵⁰

Secularisation covered every area of education, beginning with nurseries and ending with universities as well as every institution of emergency care and education such as dormitories and orphanages. Secularisation was always linked to a question about the influence that nuns had on children and young people. An issue about young people was always raised in reports about the hostile activities of nuns submitted to the Ministry of Public Security. Those reports underlined that "*convents by their intense activities are aiming to subordinate young people to convents' ideology and distort their character, convents make difficult to raise young people with a materialistic world-view*".⁵¹ School authorities, trying to pretend that decisions made by them were legal carried out tendentious visits to monastic schools. The main goal was to decide whether a school met all the standards required to obtain state rights. Usually reports had a positive opinion about the level of education and administration of the schools and a negative opinion about the ideological upbringing. The Primate issued an instruction saying that the headteachers of monastic schools mustn't allow the state inspectors to come in without the church authorities' consent.⁵²

The process of closing down schools was carried out in two stages. The first happened with immediate effect. The school authorities were informed about the closing down of institutions and asked to explain all the accusations that were made. Next, the answer was recognised to be unsatisfactory and the last step was to issue a decision about closing down the school. The second, gradual stage was based on the fact that schools

50 AAN, Office of Denominations' Affairs, sign. 5c/6, Catholic high schools.

51 A IPN BU, sign. 01283/1061, Hostile activities of convents and a work of second section for 1955.

52 KACZMAREK, A.: *Dlaczego przeszkadzały*, p. 150.

were allowed to have new children in the first grade but they couldn't have new children in different classes. As a consequence, the number of children in the upper grades was reduced until the expiration of school.⁵³ The Episcopate supported nuns in the battle about schools' and institutions' abilities to carry out emergency care and education as well as their abilities to fulfil their teaching mission.

6. Looking for new alternatives to the authorities' decision – a convent's response to a ban on educating nuns

At the same time, nuns were unable to attend higher education, vocational, high school or any other courses. Those who had been studying already weren't allowed to take a general education exam and very often the condition of taking off the religious habit was set. Nuns who were removed from schools and crossed out from a list of pupils or listeners protested by writing to authorities but usually the complaint was left with no answer. In June 1954, a superior general of the Sisters of Mercy from Warsaw was expelled from a nursing school. She lodged a complaint to the chairman of the Bierut Ministry Council and was told that sisters were expelled not because they were nuns but because they had hidden this fact.

Convents were looking for a way to enable nuns who weren't allowed to study in state institutions to receive a general education certificate. At that time, the Diocesan Institute of Catechesis, led by the Ursulines of the Roman Union, played an important role.⁵⁴ It was supposed to prepare nuns to teach religion in schools but due to the situation that had arisen, nuns were excluded from education in state schools and two classes of a develop-

53 MEZGLEWSKI, A.: *Szkolnictwo wyznaniowe*, p. 224.

54 A Higher Catechetical Institute in Cracow, Based on the Prince Cardinal Adam Sapiecha's cornerstone establishing the Diocesan Institute of Catechesis by the convents of by the Ursulines of the Roman Union in Cracow, in 15th of September 1951 the Inter-religious orders Higher Institute of Catechesis started its activities. KNAPCZYK, A. S.: *Międzszakonny Wyższy Instytut Katechetyczny w Krakowie*. In: MAJKA, J. (ed.): *Wyższe Szkolnictwo Kościelne w Polsce. Wizja kardynała Karola Wojtyły i jej realizacja*. Kraków 2002, pp. 423 – 450; SONDEJ, C. M.: *Intelektualna i duchowa formacja osobowości katechety w Międzszakonnym Wyższym Instytucie Katechetycznym w Krakowie. Studium z zakresu katechetyki*. Kraków 1998; DYDUCH, J.: *Geneza, rozwój i aktualny stan prawny Międzszakonnego Wyższego Instytutu Katechetycznego*. In: KLICH, A. E. (ed.): *Kontemplacja Oblicza Chrystusa i ewangelizacja*. Kraków 2003, pp. 31 – 44; KRZYWDA, J. – SONDEJ, C. M.: *Międzszakonny Wyższy Instytut Katechetyczny w służbie Kościoła*. In: KOPEREK, S. – SZCZUR, S. – LEŚNIAK, M. (eds.): *Archidiecezja Krakowska na przełomie tysiącleci*. Kraków 2004, pp. 499 – 509.

ing four-year course for nuns who finished primary school were opened. This course was based on a high school programme, with theological and pedagogical subjects. The graduates prepared to take a state secondary school examination.⁵⁵ The next step was to establish a Higher Catechetical Institute, which prepared nuns, by studying theology, philosophy and monastic life, not only for catechetical work but also for the Christian Ministry and Formation.⁵⁶

7. *Catechesis in parishes*

A ban on religious people teaching religion constituted an administrative obstacle and aimed to cause more organisational problems for the church authorities, which were already struggling to find enough religious teachers to teach religion at schools. It was aimed directly at a group of over 2,000 priests and nuns who taught religion. It also affected a large group of children and young people who were left without the experience of religious teaching⁵⁷. Bishops protested against the regulations from 4 August, saying that: “*removing, by the Ministry of Education, religious people and stopping them from teaching religion is against the Constitution and the Agreement because it discriminates against people, it decreases hours of religion at school and it disappoints a lot of Catholic families.*”⁵⁸ The Episcopal School Commission was aware of having a weak point in this clash with the school authorities, which was the pedagogical preparation of teachers.

The removal of religion from schools was undoubtedly the Church’s failure but the state authorities’ success was doubtful. Although the secularisation of education was conducted without a big disturbance, it is difficult to hide the fact that this action was carried out by using hidden political, economical and police pressure. The removal of religion from public schools deprived the authorities of supervising the subject, as well as the Church’s educational influence, for at least two generations of young Poles. An attempt to liquidate this inconvenience, with the August 1961 regulation issued by the Ministry of Education, met with failure. Moreover

55 KNAPCZYK, A. S.: *Międzyzakonny Wyższy Instytut Katechetyczny w Krakowie*, p. 427.

56 Ibid.

57 KONOPKA, H.: *Religia w szkołach Polski Ludowej*, p. 225.

58 Ibid., p. 228.

it caused more difficulties connected with registration and supervision issues over the catechetical point, which lasted until the end of Gomulka's government.⁵⁹

By 1962, nuns' official and team work among children and young people in church institutions and social organisations was over. A lot of nuns lost their jobs. Some of them tried in vain to return to state educational institutions. The authorities thought that: nuns should be fired and no one should care about their situation because this problem should be solved by convents, which should look after those nuns.⁶⁰ The authorities were afraid of having nuns in schools and educational institutions because they were believed to be leaders who will be carrying out clergies' work.⁶¹ They decided to stop educating nuns and splitting them up around the country.⁶² Despite all the difficulties, the nuns' educational influence didn't weaken but due to their huge involvement in catechetical work, the number of children and young people among whom they worked increased instead.⁶³

A battle with after-school catechesis, especially with those nuns who were involved in catechesis, was prepared very carefully and covered all aspects of life. It is worth pointing out an issue about the social insurance of people teaching religion. In October 1971, the Union on Denominational Politics decided that the authorities wouldn't allow religious people to teach in schools; as a result they weren't allowed to use their social insurance. The Church discussed this matter with the Social Insurance Institution, which wasn't allowed to sign any agreement. The Office on Denominational Affairs postponed the problem. In 1975, a minister of work, wages and social affairs announced that only people who were employed by an employer (parishes included) had the right to insure themselves. Religious education was classified as a fulfilment of spiritual or monastic vocation,

59 DUDEK, A.: *Państwo a Kościół w Polsce 1945-1979*. Warszawa 1995, p. 93.

60 Protokół z posiedzenia Komisji KC ds. Kleru w dn. 26 lipca 1961 r. In: *Tajne dokumenty*, p. 19.

61 *Ibid.*, p. 18.

62 *Ibid.*

63 MIREK, A.: Zaangażowanie sióstr zakonnych w pracę katechetyczną wśród dzieci i młodzieży w okresie PRL jako jedno z priorytetowych zadań wspólnot zakonnych na przykładzie Zgromadzenia Córek Maryi Niepokalanej. In: J. SZCZEPANIAK, J. (ed.): *Materiały i studia do dziejów nauczania i wychowania religijnego*, t. 4. Kraków 2004, p. 138.

that's why it was beyond the employer-employee relationship. The issue about insurance remained a convenient measure of pressure. During a conversation on 3 December 1976 with Bishop Bronisław Dąbrowski, Stanisław Kania, a secretary of the Central Committee of the Polish United Workers' Party, announced that nuns who taught religion couldn't have any insurance because: "*We believe that nuns who are praying or teaching religion are not allowed to have insurance because they don't do useful social work.*"⁶⁴ Religious education remained, according to the authorities, useless for state citizens. However, over 90 percent of members of the Polish United Workers' Party believed that children should learn religion because it guaranteed the best moral education.

The fact is that Communism didn't destroyed religious lessons taught by people properly prepared and delegated by the Church. Nuns who were discriminated against by the communist authorities constituted 20 percent of all religious teachers, teaching outside schools. Millions of Poles received basic knowledge and a Christian formation thanks to them.

Conclusion

Knowing that both the dissolution of a one-off system and regaining independence in Poland (after the Yalta Conference) was unreal, the part of society that didn't accept the new communist system decided to work with great effort, planting the embryo of independent thinking and resistance in the name of law and the defence of values, as well as stirring up others who were less brave. Anti-communist resistance in the People's Republic of Poland applied to every class and group of society. It was undertaken, not only by the armed Underground, but also by Polish society, which felt the need to join the resistance in whatever form. The Great Primate didn't expect the People's Republic of Poland to weaken (in the near future) and was afraid of any violent shock that might result in Soviet intervention. He was strictly against profuse in with Polish blood. Instead he saw an opportunity for a gradual evolution of the system and extension of freedom of religion and civil rights. His strategy was a combination of both adjustment and resistance and was different from other strategies held

64 Sprawozdanie z rozmowy ks. bp. B. Dąbrowskiego z S. Kanią sekretarzem KC PZPR z dnia 3 grudnia 1976 r. In: RAINA, P.: *Rozmowy z władzami PRL. Arcybiskup Dąbrowski w służbie Kościoła i narodu, t. 1*, Warszawa 1995, p. 275.

by the other great hierarch of Eastern Europe – the Primate of Hungary, Józef Mindszenty.

The described symptoms of adjustment were accompanied by keeping an internal sovereignty and an ability to make resistance at least against some of the system features or government acts. The resistance was directed at issues limiting freedom of denomination, breaching the values of national traditions or limiting freedom of speech and beliefs.

Real Christian life shown by Polish nuns in their dull everyday routine was the most effective picture of anti-communist action. This was the reason why the authorities were afraid of the nuns' presence in society and tried, with perseverance and firmness, to push them into the dregs of society.

Affirmation, adjustment, resistance and opposition – these attitudes appeared at the same time and were related to each other. Nuns, as well as the whole of society, were forced to remain silent and follow the rules. They got used to it but at the same time they tried to keep autonomy in certain areas and to extend it. These activities were effective. Discrepancies between guidelines from different instances and real life might be the proof. The history of the People's Republic of Poland might be described as a process of struggle between the authorities and society where both sides were changing under the influence of this struggle.

Resumé

Protikomunistický odboj v Poľskej ľudovej republike sa spájal s každou skupinou a triedou spoločnosti. Odboj sa netýkal iba ozbrojeného ilegálneho hnutia, ale takmer väčšiny spoločnosti, ktorá cítila potrebu kolektívneho odporu, i keď z hľadiska formy tu boli rozdiely. Spomedzi spoločenských skupín, ktoré vykonávali protikomunistickú činnosť zohrala Katolícka cirkev, ako aj ženské rehole fungujúce v rámci cirkvi, dôležitú úlohu. Svojou účasťou na vzdelávaní a starostlivosti o deti, ktoré im boli zverené do opatery, vytvorili u detí a mládeže protikomunistické povedomie. Legislatíva komunistických orgánov mala za cieľ vytlačiť činnosť reholí zo spoločenského života a viedla k úplnej likvidácii ženských kláštorov v Poľsku. Navzdory vytlačaniu oficiálnej činnosti ženských reholí zatváraním inštitúcií, kde učili a ošetrovali mníšky, ony použili rôzne formy apoštolátu a odboja proti komunistickému režimu.

Prostredníctvom svojej tichej a skrytej práce učili poľské mníšky mladých ľudí hodnotám, ktoré boli v opozícii voči materialistickému

obrazu sveta, ktorý budoval a vyučoval oficiálny vzdelávací systém. Pravý kresťanský život, ktorým mníšky žili, bol tým najúčinnnejším obrazom protikomunistickej činnosti. Preto sa úrady obávali prítomnosti mníšok v spoločenskom živote a vytrvalo a tvrdo sa pokúšali vytlačiť ich na okraj spoločnosti.